

NEW MATERIAL REMOVAL TOOLS AND PROCESSES TO SAFELY EXPEDITE MAINTENANCE ON COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Maintenance actions for aircraft and other systems often require removal of materials of various types from locations throughout the structure. The lack of effective, reliable nonmetallic tools for maintainers often drives the use of unapproved metal tools and/or unacceptable methods for material removal. The United States Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL) and the University of Dayton Research Institute (UDRI) developed a suite of efficient nonmetallic material removal tools that do not damage underlying composite structure. These include flat scraper blades for multiple applications, three types of tools to remove fillers from gaps of varying widths and cutters for removal of adhesive and sealant remaining on a structure after failure of bonded nutplates. Many of the tools were inspired by existing metallic tools that could readily remove the materials of interest but pose significant damage risk for structure. The new tools are injection molded from Solvay Engineered Plastics' Torlon polyamide-imide (PAI) resin, and their development was undertaken in close cooperation with aircraft maintainers to ensure useful final products. Required accessories were identified or developed, and procedures for tool use were written to maximize material removal efficiency and increase the tools' working lives. All tools are commercially available under the EnduroSharp[™] trade name.

1 INTRODUCTION

Maintenance actions for aircraft and other systems often require removal of materials of various types from locations throughout the structure, including gaps and hard-to-access areas. Materials that may need to be removed from composite substrates include sealants, adhesives, gap fillers, caulks, boots, tapes, elastomeric coatings, and pressure sensitive adhesive (PSA) residue. Nonmetallic tools are typically specified for material removal to reduce damage potential to underlying structures, but these tools tend to be ineffective and unreliable. This often drives maintainers to use unapproved tools and/or unacceptable methods to reduce removal time, which has resulted in damage to vehicles, causing the need for repairs and reduction in system availability [1]. Figure 1 shows typical ineffective nonmetallic material removal tools and a removal practice that risks structural damage.

Under contract to the United States Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL), the University of Dayton Research Institute (UDRI) developed and commercialized a suite of improved nonmetallic tools for a variety of material removal applications [2]. AFRL and UDRI are transitioning these tools, along with the required accessories and associated procedures, to aerospace and other customers. When used properly, the new tools do not damage composite structure and reduce material removal times when compared to other nonmetallic options.

Figure 1: Typical ineffective nonmetallic removal tools (left); unsafe removal practice (right).

2 APPROACH

The design process for new tools began by identifying key areas on aerospace vehicles requiring material removal and the types of materials that must be removed. Ineffective tools currently used were identified and their deficiencies were studied. In addition, unauthorized metallic tools were evaluated to determine the attributes that allow them to effectively remove relevant materials. The inability of nonmetallic tools to maintain sharp edges was identified as their greatest deficiency. This leads to the need for frequent sharpening and/or the use of many of the short-lived tools to complete a job, increasing both time and cost associated with material removal. Given the variety of applications identified, it was readily apparent multiple tool types, beyond just variations on shapes and sizes of standard scraper blades, were required to effectively address the problem. Therefore, new tool configurations and new materials of construction had to be determined, with the intent of final fabrication by injection molding for affordability.

Inspiration for several of the new designs was taken from existing metallic tools, and development was an iterative process as adjustments were made based on testing and evaluations. The latter were conducted both in the laboratory and by aircraft maintainers to assess material removal efficiency, tool life, and the impact on composite substrates. As much as possible, machined prototypes were assessed during the developmental process to avoid costs associated with procuring injection molding tools that may have to be modified or even abandoned as changes were required. Final evaluations were always conducted on the injection molded versions of the material removal tools before commercialization. Close working relationships with key customers were established early in the development process to ensure new tools met maintainers' needs and became authorized for use upon availability, while continual interactions with suppliers sped delivery of these affordable, useful tools.

3 NEW NONMETALLIC MATERIAL REMOVAL TOOLS

UDRI developed five families of nonmetallic tools: flat scraper blades for a variety of removal applications; bits, blades and discs for gap filler removal; and cutters to remove residual adhesive and sealant associated with failed bonded nutplates. Each family includes multiple tool sizes, as specified by AFRL's customers, as well as accessories needed to effect material removal. Some tool development and testing details are provided below, with additional data published elsewhere [3, 4].

3.1 Gap Filler Removal Bits (GFR-Bits)

The first material application AFRL and UDRI addressed was removal of two specific fillers (one harder and one softer) from gaps with dimensions approximately 6.35 mm wide by 6.35 mm deep (0.25 in x 0.25 in). Thin nonmetallic tools, such as scraper blades or hooks, were generally specified to remove these fillers. These tools may cut material at the bottom of a gap but tend to tear filler material from gap side walls as they are moved along a filled gap. This makes the tools inefficient and difficult to push through the filler, and it results in filler remaining on gap side walls. Prior to gap filler removal with a narrow scraper, a razor blade is often used to detach filler from side walls, but this practice can induce damage to composite substrates. Other more efficient processes, typically using metallic tools, can also cause damage to composites. The concept selected to overcome existing gap filler removal deficiencies was a rotary bit based on available metal bits shown to readily remove the materials. Four configurations were assessed: straight and spiral bits with both single and double flutes (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Metal bit configurations evaluated for nonmetallic tool.

Molds made from the metal bits were used to cast nonmetallic counterparts of the four configurations from a polyurethane resin. Both carbon/epoxy and carbon/bismaleimide (BMI) test panels were manufactured to create simulated gaps, which were filled with flexibilized epoxy material for removal trials using the polyurethane bits mounted in a battery-powered electric drill. The bits were not durable enough to remove the minimum amount of filler per bit desired by maintainers, which was about 91 linear cm (36 in). Since some commercial scraper blades are manufactured using Ultem® polyetherimide resin, this material (fiber-filled and unfilled) was selected for evaluation. Bits could not be cast using Ultem, and their geometries were too complicated to machine from stock, so it was necessary to produce a low-grade steel prototype injection mold to fabricate Ultem bits. Trials were conducted with the bits mounted on a 20,000 revolutions per minute (rpm) pneumatic die grinder with feed air regulated at 620 kPa (90 psi), since battery-powered drills are often not permitted for aircraft maintenance. Ultem bits showed improved durability over urethane bits and caused no damage to composite substrates, but these tools still did not achieve the desired gap filler removal per bit.

Six additional material combinations were injection molded and evaluated, including unfilled and filled versions of polyether ether ketone (PEEK™), which is also found in commercial scraper blades. This work showed promise, with some bits removing more than 30 cm (12 in) of filler with minimal effort required by the operator and negligible damage to the bits, as determined by visual examinations and mass loss calculations. It also highlighted the importance of bit rotational speed, which must be at a high enough rpm to move through gap filler without bogging down but not so high as to excessively wear the bit. Tests using a number of rotational speeds led to selection of 6,000 rpm as a good compromise between gap filler removal efficiency and bit longevity. Lastly, these trials identified spiral single flute bits manufactured from filled materials as the most durable.

At the suggestion of the injection molder, three filled versions of Torlon PAI thermoplastic were evaluated. Torlon can be injection molded with some difficulty, and the resultant components subsequently develop superior properties after an extended curing process that transforms them from thermoplastics to cross-linked thermosets [5]. Bits made from Torlon in this way do not soften as they are heated due to friction during use; they simply degrade when their service temperature of about 260 °C (500 °F) is reached. This helps Torlon bits maintain their sharp edges and improves their durability. Torlon also has high strength and stiffness, and it is resistant to most solvents and chemicals found in the aircraft operational and maintenance environments. Spiral single flute versions of 30 percent fiberglass filled PAI (Torlon 5030) proved to be the most robust while also achieving some of the best gap filler removal rates. Figure 3 shows two of these bits and the gap filler removal process.

Additional evaluations were conducted using Torlon 5030 bits to more thoroughly assess material removal rate and potential for damage to composite substrates. The bits were operated at approximately 6,000 rpm by using a 12,000 rpm pneumatic die grinder with air pressure set between 241 and 310 kPa (35-45 psi). The 12,000 rpm die grinder was able to deliver desired bit rotational speed without the loss of torque seen when operating the 20,000 rpm die grinder at the reduced pressure required to achieve 6,000 rpm. Carbon/epoxy and carbon/BMI test panels were configured such that disassembly was possible to enable close examination of bottoms and side walls of simulated gaps after use of bits to remove filler. Both the substrates and the used bits were examined under

magnification to assess damage or degradation. Though remnant Torlon and fiberglass filler was seen on composite substrates, no composite damage was incurred and bit wear was minimal. Removal trials showed a single GFR-Bit could remove 90 cm of filler, meeting the requirement, and could do so in 3 to 5 minutes, depending on the filler material.

Figure 3: GFR-Bits (left) and their use on a die grinder to remove gap filler.

3.2 Torlon Scraper Blades (TSBs)

AFRL and UDRI then turned their attention to improving standard scraper blades for removal of several customer-specified materials, including elastomeric coatings, boots, tapes and PSA residue. The starting point was existing nonmetallic blades fabricated from Ultem and PEEK that did not perform as desired, though they offered an improvement at the time they were introduced. These blades do not hold cutting edges well and are difficult to properly sharpen. They readily disengaged from the material being removed due to their flexibility, and this is exacerbated as the blades dull during use. In applications that required heat-assisted removal, Ultem and PEEK blades soften and quickly lose their cutting edges. It was clear a change in tool configuration and material of construction was needed. Torlon 5030 was chosen as the new scraper material based on its stiffness and service temperature, as well as experience gained during development of the GFR-Bits.

Extruded Torlon 5030 sheet stock approximately 6.35 mm (0.25 in) thick was machined into prototype blade configurations and evaluated both in the laboratory and by aircraft maintainers in operational environments. The ability to machine prototypes allowed final configurations to be determined before the need to purchase costly injection molds. Prototype blades were fabricated in several sizes, mostly to mimic those of available Ultem and PEEK blades. The key geometric feature of the new blades is the $25^{\circ}/25^{\circ}$ asymmetrical 1/3-2/3 cutting tip, as shown in Figure 4. This feature, when used properly, eliminates the extreme pressure that must be placed on cutting edges for other tool designs and allows TSBs to better maintain their sharp cutting edges. Pressure is mostly applied to one of the feet (Figure 4) rather than the cutting tip, and the blade can be slightly rotated on the foot to find the best angle for engagement in the material to be removed.

Laboratory and field trials were conducted on machined prototypes to evaluate speed and ease of material removal. TSBs were used with a commercially available handles and a commercially available pneumatic tool adapted to receive the blades. When final blade geometries were determined, UDRI worked closely with a tool maker and an injection molder to design tools for injection molded TSBs. Several design iterations were required to ensure desired attributes, such as blade stiffness, were not sacrificed while striving for ease of manufacture and affordability. Final evaluations were conducted both in the laboratory and by aircraft maintainers to ensure the injection molded versions removed material as well as the machined prototypes. In the laboratory, blade dimensional tolerances were assessed to ensure they fit handles, sectioned blades were checked and found to contain negligible porosity and blades were tested in a three-point bend configuration to determine strength, which exceeded those of the fielded Ultem and PEEK scrapers. In addition, more thorough laboratory evaluations were conducted to assess the impact of TSBs on composite substrates.

Figure 4: TSB's 25°/25° asymmetrical 1/3-2/3 cutting tip.

All five TSB sizes were evaluated on primed and unprimed carbon/epoxy test panels using a pneumatic tool operated using 620 kPa (90 psi) air pressure to drive the blades to simulate a removal process. The evaluation consisted of multiple passes over twelve test areas on each test panel, with the designed tool angle of 25° to the surface maintained for a given blade on six test areas and a tool angle of 45° to the surface maintained for the other six to increase chances of damage. The blades directly contacted the test panels and were not used to remove material from the panels (the panels were uncoated), though the force applied as the blades traversed test panel surfaces was considered to be on the high end of that required to remove elastomeric coatings and tape. This force was estimated during actual material removal from sample specimens placed on a Cole-Parmer® scale. The load range seen on the scale was recorded as the operator removed material. The operator became proficient at duplicating this load range and applied it while moving the blades across the test panels. A portion of the test matrix for unprimed panels is shown in Table 1, with the last column providing the load ranges determined using the scale. Only the tests for TSB-1200, which is the 30.5 mm (1.2 in) wide blade, are illustrated in the table, whereas the complete test matrix included the same tests for the other four TSB widths. An analogous test matrix was executed using the primed composite test panel (six passes at both 25° and 45° blade angles for each of the five TSB configurations).

Panel ID	Specimen ID	Blade Style	Part Number	Blade Angle to Surface, Degrees	Number of Passes	Elapsed Time, Seconds	Test Area, Millimeters (inches)	Load, Kilograms (pounds)
UPC-1	UPC-1-1	TSB	TSB-1200	25	6	15.85	30.5 x 88.9 (1.20 x 3.5)	4.8-6.0 (10.6-13.2)
UPC-1	UPC-1-6	TSB	TSB-1200	45	6	17.42	30.5 x 88.9 (1.20 x 3.5)	5.1-6.6 (11.2-14.6)

Table 1: Abbreviated test matrix for evaluating TSB effects on composite substrates.

Extensive visual examinations were made of all test panel surfaces and used blades after testing. In no cases were composite panels damaged; magnified views showed no exposed test panel fibers and no subsurface cracks caused by TSB passes over the test area. Remnant Torlon material from blades, including some filler fibers, were found on test panels. In a couple instances, small amounts of primer were removed without damaging the composite material below. Photo documentation for an unprimed composite test panel using the TSB-1200 blade is provided in Figure 5. Section (1) of the figure shows the overall view of the test area (right) and the TSB that contacted the test area during the simulated material removal process (left). The green arrow identifies the portion of the TSB that made contact with the test panel surface. The regions of the test panel identified as START and MIDDLE indicate locations where the TSB began each pass and the midway point along each pass, respectively. Section (2) images for the START (A) and MIDDLE (B) test areas were taken to the right of the yellow dots found in the section (1) image. Black arrows indicate increasing magnification. The red arrow in the highest-magnification image points to glass filler fibers from the TSB. Section (3) provides SEM photomicrographs taken from the test area at locations indicated by the red arrows in the section (1) test area image, with (A) being a cross-sectional view of the test area at the start of a TSB pass across the test panel and (B) showing a cross-section taken from the test area near the midway point of the TSB pass. The spaces between the black arrows in these two cross-sectional images define the distance over which the TSB was in contact with test panel surface. The portion of (B) enclosed in the black

box is shown in increased magnification in (C). As evidenced by the cross-sections, there were no cracks below the surface of the panel caused by TSB interaction with the surface. Figure 6 shows minor damage to the TSB-1200 that traversed the primed panel at a 45° angle, as well as damage to primer caused by use of a narrower TSBs on the primed test panel (inside the red circles).

Figure 5: Visual examination of test panel after simulated removal process using a TSB-1200.

Figure 6: TSB-1200 blade after simulated removal process (left); TSB damage to primer (right).

The TSBs' configuration and their Torlon 5030 construction allow these blades to keep their sharp edges longer than other nonmetallic blades. In addition, they are easily sharpened using standard abrasive papers in the 120-180 grit range. During one design iteration, the parting line for the injection molded blades was moved to align it with the blade tip (off-center due to the blades' asymmetrical nature) to provide an easy means of ensuring the 1/3-2/3 cutting tip remains intact during sharpening (Figure 4). The five available TSB configurations are shown in Figure 7. The far-right images in the figure show another advantage of using Torlon for scraper blade construction, which is the ability to readily modify TSBs using standard metal machining processes. Any number of shapes can be generated for specific applications, such as removing sealant from around fasteners.

Figure 7: Front and back views of the five TSB sizes; blades machined to unique shapes (right).

3.3 Torlon Gap Blades (TGBs)

Though GFR-Bits improve gap filler removal for a few specific applications, these tools have several shortcomings, including their design for one specific gap that is fairly wide. The bits could be used to remove filler from wider gaps but they are less efficient when used this way, and many gaps of interest are narrower rather than wider than the bits' 4.1 mm (0.162 in) diameter. The GFR-Bit concept is not suited for narrow gaps since smaller-diameter bits would easily break during use. In addition, GFR-Bits cannot remove very soft materials, such as polysulfide sealant, since these gum up the bits and cause them to fail after a few centimeters of removal. GFR-Bits also create large amounts of filler debris during use, and the bits cannot be used for partial depth removal of fillers, which is desired for some applications. For these reasons, UDRI and AFRL developed a novel family of TGBs that safely expedite gap filler removal while overcoming GFR-Bit limitations.

The design concept for TGBs was based on a commercially available sheet metal ripper but using replaceable blades of varying widths and depths along with an adapter that couples them to the handles and pneumatic tool adopted for TSBs. Figure 8 shows a sheet metal ripper in the left image, line drawings for the TGB design concept in the center and prototype TGBs with adapters on the right. Three cutting edges were incorporated into the TGBs (Figure 9). These include edges along the sides of the cutting surface designed to shear gap filler rather than tear it using brute force from gap side walls, providing an easier and faster transition through the filled gap and quicker gap filler removal. The TGB cutting surface enters the gap while the remainder of the tool rides along the top surface on either side of the gap. Prototype TGBs were machined from a 12.7 mm (0.5 in) thick extruded Torlon 5030 sheet, and the adapter was machined from 25.4 mm (1 in) thick unfilled DuPont™ Delrin® thermoplastic. Prototype TGBs of several widths, each with multiple cutting depths, were evaluated in the laboratory and by maintainers in the field. An incremental process for gap filler removal was adopted, with the shallowest blade being used first, followed by the next and finally by the TGB with the largest cutting depth. The three-step process minimized effort required to remove filler and actually reduced removal time versus attempting to push through the full depth of filler using just the deepest blade. With the incremental process, the final blade used is angled in the gap to facilitate removal from side walls. If twisted too much, a blade will break rather than damage the composite structure. Field trials and other end-user inputs identified the final five widths and three depths for production TGBs.

Figure 8: Sheet metal ripper (left); TGB concept (center); prototype adapters and TGBs (right).

Figure 9: TGB features, including cutting width, cutting depth and three cutting edges.

Injection molds were procured to produce the 15 identified TGB configurations from Torlon 5030 and gap blade adapters from Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU). Field-level maintainer evaluations of the injection molded versions verified these tools performed as well as the prototypes. Laboratory tests indicated the injection molded blades met the desired dimensional tolerances and contained virtually no porosity. Extensive laboratory testing was conducted, similar to that for TSBs using primed and

unprimed simulated gap test panels that could be disassembled for in-depth examination of gap bottoms and side walls, to assess the potential for TGBs to damage composite structure. TGBs were used in six separate passes over the same area in one test and in a single pass over a separate area for another test. These tests provided results similar to those obtained for TSBs, with no damage caused to composite test panels. In a few instances, TGBs damaged primer but never harmed the composite panel underneath. Evidence of Torlon 5030 (resin and filler fibers) was seen on some test panels. Figure 10 shows the unprimed and primed test panels, as well as gap filler removal on a separate panel showing TGBs generate much less debris than GFR-Bits during gap filler removal.

Figure 10: Unprimed and primed composite test panels; gap filler removal with a TGB (right).

3.4 Gap Filler Removal (GFR) Discs

One additional tool concept was created to address gaps narrower than 1.9 mm, which was the smallest width TGB considered robust enough to commercialize. Eight disc-like configurations fabricated from Torlon 5030 were developed for use with oscillating power tools (also known as multi-tools) to remove filler from gaps as narrow as 1.5 mm (0.060 in). The discs are configured to work with a variety of pneumatic and battery-driven multi-tools. The oscillating action allows the 1.4 mm (0.055 in) wide discs to remove certain gap fillers without damaging underlying composite structure. The same disc concept would not be durable and would readily damage composites if used in a rotary rather than oscillating mode. Gap filler removal using GFR Discs does generate significant small debris. Evaluations of machined prototypes and injection molded discs conducted in the field by maintainers and in the laboratory, including extensive tests to assess potential for composite damage, delivered favorable results. Figure 11 shows the eight GFR Disc configurations alongside a photograph of filler removal using the full-round version. The disc is oscillating, not rotating, so the same portion of the disc stays engaged during the process. A disc can be removed from the oscillating tool, rotated and reinstalled to access unused portions of the disc for material removal.

Figure 11: GFR Discs (left) and gap filler removal using a full-round disc on an oscillating tool.

3.5 Torlon Adhesive Cutter (TAC)

Adhesively bonded nutplates are often employed in the fabrication of aerospace structures and can be found on some vehicles in the tens of thousands. Utilized for the same reasons as mechanically fastened nutplates, where two-sided access is not possible during assembly and/or where quick access for maintenance is necessary, bonded nutplates have the advantages of reducing stress concentrations in structures (via elimination of rivet holes), reducing installation/production costs and potentially

saving weight. Figure 12 shows one style of nutplate alongside a photograph of many nutplates on a structure during adhesive cure. The colorful fixtures holding the nutplates in place and applying pressure are removed after the adhesive is cured.

Figure 12: Dome style nutplate (left); many nutplates in place during adhesive cure (right).

Bonded nutplates fail for a number of reasons, including poor preparation of nutplate or structure bond surfaces, use of the wrong grip length nut element forcing failure of the adhesive, fasteners locking up in nut elements due to excessive frictional heat during installation and improper fastener torque sequencing for panel installation forcing failure of the adhesive. The often lengthy time required to remove a failed nutplate and reinstall a new one can be a disadvantage of bonded nutplates versus their riveted counterparts. One issue is the difficulty associated with safe removal of residual sealant and adhesive from failed nutplate locations before installation on new nutplates, which usually must be conducted via hand abrasion and requires at least tens of minutes and can take up to several hours of work to accomplish in difficult-to-access areas.

TSBs were shown to remove nutplate adhesive but could not access many of the required locations on aircraft. Therefore, TACs were developed using Torlon 5030 specifically for removing remnant adhesive and sealant from failed bonded nutplate locations and were based on commercially available metallic reverse counterbores. The cutters remove a circular section of material just large enough to accommodate the desired nutplate, which is important given the close proximity of many nutplates. Aircraft maintainers for a specific system identified their highest-priority nutplates, which then drove the cutter sizes created. TACs in each of these sizes were designed in two different configurations to function with the pneumatic tools used to prepare surfaces for nutplate bonding. One is the Surface Preparation Tool from the Andrews Tool Co. (Andrews Tool) that can quickly access nutplates near the periphery of a part and the other is a drill motor used with a mandrel inserted into the fastener hole associated with the nutplate (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Andrews Tool with TAC (above) and drill motor with TAC on mandrel (below).

Concept TACs were first 3-D printed to check form and fit, then machined prototypes were fabricated from Torlon 5030 rod stock. These were evaluated by aircraft maintainers and in the laboratory, where it was determined the rotational speed of the cutters should be about 500-600 rpm to allow successful material removal while maintaining cutter durability. Subsequent laboratory and field assessments showed injection molded cutters were slightly more efficient at removing material than the machined prototypes. cursory testing showed TACs do not damage composite structure, and separate extensive tests confirmed mandrels used with the drill motor do not damage fastener holes. At the request of aircraft maintainers, segmented tetherable mandrels were developed for the drill motor to allow cutters and mandrels to be ‘fished’ through structure to reach hard-to-access locations. Swivels were added so the tethers would not spin with the rotating tool.

A TAC requires just one or two minutes to remove excess adhesive (and sealant, if present) to the point only a thin layer is present and surface preparation for bonding a new nutplate can commence using abrasive pads. Abrasion required to prepare the area for bonding a new nutplate can be typically accomplished using three abrasive pads if the TAC is first employed to remove the bulk of the remnant adhesive, whereas up to ten abrasive pads are required to remove the adhesive and prepare the surface properly without use of the TAC since the adhesive readily gums up the abrasive pads. One TAC can be used to remove material from many failed nutplate locations, and TAC cutting surfaces can be sharpened with standard abrasive paper (120-180 grit). Figure 14 shows a TAC on a drill motor removing adhesive from a test panel. A TAC and an abrasive pad are depicted after adhesive removal in Figure 15. The abrasive pad shown is one of at least five required to remove the same amount of adhesive that one TAC alone can readily remove. TAC kits, with cutters and accessories for the Andrews Tool and drill motor, are shown in Figure 16.

Figure 14: Adhesive removal from test panel using a TAC on a drill motor.

Figure 15: TAC (left) and abrasive pad (right) after adhesive removal.

Figure 16: AFRL two-layer TAC kit with drill motor (left) and Andrews Tool (right).

4 COMMERCIALIZATION

AFRL and UDRI worked closely with their customers throughout the entire development and evaluation processes for all material removal tools to ensure final products met specified needs. UDRI also worked with injection molders and injection mold manufacturers to ensure final designs worked as well as the successfully demonstrated prototypes machined from Torlon 5030 sheet or rod stock. Torlon material removal tools are available under the EnduroSharp™ trade name from the injection molder that worked with UDRI during development, Performance Plastics, Ltd (PPL) in Cincinnati, Ohio, USA. The commercially available products include GFR-Bits, five widths of TSBs, fifteen TGBs (five widths, each with the same three depths), eight GFR Disc configurations and a variety of TAC sizes, as well as a number of kits.

A wide range of accessories were identified or developed and also made commercially available. Some were existing items, such as die grinders, drill motors and oscillating tools. Others were modified or improved versions of existing items, such as the adapted pneumatic tool for use with scraper and gap blades. In many cases new accessories were designed and commercialized. These include the gap blade adapter, mandrels and swivels for adhesive cutters, specialized wrenches and a “T” handle for manual operation to safely use abrasive pads on composites. An improved handle for use with scraper and gap blades is more robust than the handle used during development phases and eliminates that handle’s metal clip that could damage structure during some removal processes. A sanding fixture was also commercialized to hold scraper blades at the correct 25° angle during sharpening. In addition to hardware, procedures were developed to maximize tool efficiency and durability [6]. The commercially available AFRL/UDRI tools with accessories are shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Commercialized Torlon material removal tools and accessories.

5 CONCLUSIONS

AFRL and UDRI developed several new and improved nonmetallic tools intended to increase material removal efficiency and reduce damage to aircraft structure during the removal process. These GFR-Bits, TSBs, TGBs, GFR Discs and TACs are manufactured from Torlon 5030 (fiberglass reinforced PAI) and provide maintainers better options for removing sealants, adhesives, gap fillers, caulks, boots, tapes, elastomeric coatings, and PSA residue from fiber-reinforced composite and metal structures.

Their unique designs and Torlon 5030 composition, coupled with proper usage techniques, enable the Torlon material removal tools to be highly efficient and durable. They maintain cutting edges better than other nonmetallic removal tools and are easily sharpened using 120-180 grit abrasive paper. Torlon 5030 provides high strength and stiffness up to 260 °C (500 °F), as well as resistance to common aircraft fluids and maintenance chemicals. The new EnduroSharp tools and accessories are commercially available and have been evaluated and approved for applications on multiple aircraft, as well as several nonaerospace applications.

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